

MANAGEMENT STRENGTHENING CHARACTER EDUCATION (PPK) THROUGH SOCIAL SCIENCE LEARNING (IPS) IN IMPROVING STUDENT ACHIEVEMENT

UJANG CEPI BARLIAN

Nusantara Islamic University, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu, Bandung.
Email: ujangcepibarlian@uninus.ac.id

INAYAH

Nusantara Islamic University, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu, Bandung.
Email: inayah@uninus.ac.id

SITI HALIMAH

Nusantara Islamic University, Jl. Soekarno Hatta No. 530, Sekejati, Kec. Buah batu, Bandung.
Email: sitihalimah@uninus.ac.id

Abstract

The background of this research is that there are phenomena that are of concern regarding the character of students in the teaching and learning process in the school environment and in the classroom, several facts were found, for example not doing homework, cheating, skipping school without permission, or being indifferent to cleanliness in the school environment, dressing who are not neat, other juvenile delinquencies due to foreign culture that continues to enter. This research aims to find out and analyze: 1) Planning for strengthening character education through social studies learning, 2) Organizing strengthening character education and 3) Implementing strengthening character education through social studies learning 2) Supervising strengthening character education through social studies learning, 3) Obstacles to strengthening education character through social studies learning, 4) Solutions in facing obstacles to strengthening character education through social studies learning, 5) Management impact of strengthening character education through social studies learning. To achieve this goal, this research uses qualitative research. The data collection techniques used were interviews, observation and documentation. Meanwhile, checking the validity of the data is carried out by diligent observation and triangulation. The implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement through social studies learning has not been optimal. The stages of management functions can be briefly described as follows: a. Schools as institutions that provide character education strengthening already have good plans to improve student achievement. b. The organization of strengthening character education in improving student achievement has not gone according to the program plan. c. The implementation of strengthening character education carried out by all interested elements in the school environment has not been optimal. The evaluation results show that student achievement has increased in social studies learning by implementing strengthening character education. d Solutions to face obstacles to the implementation of strengthening character education, namely consolidation, equalizing perceptions, improving quality standards, short-term solutions, medium-term solutions and long-term solutions.

Keywords: Strengthening Character Education, Social Studies Learning, Student Achievement.

A. INTRODUCTION

The moral crisis of the Indonesian nation is occurring at almost all levels, both in law enforcement officials, government bureaucracy, and in general society. This shows the reality that our education has not been able to complete the most basic things in human resource development and is a big challenge in national education. Facts show that the widespread phenomenon of deviant teenage behavior is dominated by students. The large number of school age teenagers who are affected by mental disorders, pornography, violence, suicide, is caused by a lack of supervision from their parents. Another cause is the influence of technological culture such as television and various other media. There are quite a few teenagers and adults whose morals are damaged because they prefer to watch television with sexual content and dangerous digital entertainment, such as ethnic humor and pornography. Internet media has a very influential role in juvenile delinquency, and can trigger bad behavior. The values of character education in social studies learning include the ability to solve problems that exist in everyday life. In social studies learning, students are expected to be able to practice these values not only during classroom learning, but also to apply them in everyday life. This aims to ensure that students have critical, systematic, creative, independent thinking and can collaborate with other people. The values mentioned above are currently known as the concept of character education.

Strengthening Character Education (PPK) through social studies learning needs to be packaged in various ways. Moreover, currently world challenges are getting bigger and the negative impact of globalization is growing among the younger generation. This is where the author's thought emerged that social studies learning can be used as a vehicle for character education management through social studies learning. Therefore, there is a need for further research related to teaching and learning activities in social studies subjects that are integrated with character education values in the schools concerned. In this study, the author is interested in examining how to manage PPK through social studies learning. The author will examine the problems faced in planning, management, implementation, assessment, obstacles and finding solutions in Strengthening Character Education through Social Studies Learning. The hope of this study is to provide an overview of the problems of Strengthening Character Education through social studies learning.

Research Question

- a. How do you plan to strengthen character education through Social Sciences (IPS) learning in improving student achievement?
- b. How does the organization of strengthening character education through Social Sciences (IPS) learning increase student achievement?
- c. How does strengthening character education through Social Sciences (IPS) learning increase student achievement?

- d. How can we control the strengthening of character education through Social Sciences (IPS) learning in improving student achievement?
- e. What are the obstacles and solutions in facing obstacles to strengthening character education through Social Sciences (IPS) learning in improving student achievement?

B. THEORETICAL STUDY

Management is a trick because management achieves targets through ways of organizing other people to carry out tasks. Meanwhile, management is seen as a profession because management is based on special skills to achieve a manager's achievements and professionals are required by a code of ethics (Barlian, 2016: 21).

Education management is activities to achieve a goal, or the process of organizing work to achieve a goal that has been set in the education system. According to Mulyasa (2016: 17), educational management is the process of developing cooperative activities of a group of people to achieve various educational goals that have been set. The process of controlling these activities includes planning, organizing, actualizing and monitoring as a process to achieve the vision into action (Hasibuan, 2018: 191).

Character Education Theory in this research the researcher uses the theory of Thomas Lickona, in this theory character education is defined as all efforts that can be made to influence students' character. More fully, Lickona states that the definition of character education is a deliberate effort to help someone so that he can understand, pay attention to and implement core ethical values.

Character education according to Lickona (2012: 34) contains three main elements, namely knowing goodness, loving goodness, and doing goodness. Character education not only teaches students what is right and what is wrong, but character education also instills good habits so that students understand, are able to feel, and want to do good.

Therefore, character education is a serious and planned effort to understand, form, and foster ethical values, both for oneself and for all members of society or citizens as a whole. From the education and character above, it can be concluded that character education is a process of instilling good values in students which includes the components of knowledge, awareness or will, and actions to implement these values, both in relationships with God Almighty, others. Humans, the environment, as well as the homeland and nation so that they become perfect humans.

Thomas Lickona explains that respect and responsibility are values that form the basis of schools which not only allow, but also require teachers to provide this education in order to develop ethically knowledgeable people who can position themselves as part of a responsible society. . Lickona (2012: 65) explains that this means showing our appreciation for the self-esteem of other people or things other than ourselves. If we respect others, it means we respect them. If we respect them, it means we will feel a measure of our responsibility to respect their well-being.

Character education in educational units is carried out in an integrative manner and is an integral part of the school-based quality improvement management program which is implemented in development, implementation and evaluation by each educational unit. In detail, the implementation of character education at the educational unit level according to the Curriculum Center of the Ministry of National Education can be carried out through learning activities, developing school culture, co-curricular or extra-curricular activities, daily activities at home and in the community, assessing success, developing curriculum at the educational unit level, as well as development stages. Thus, character education is not only at the cognitive level, but touches on internalization and real practice in students' daily lives in society.

At a macro level, character development is divided into three stages, namely planning, implementation and evaluation of results. The development in question is related to management functions, namely planning, namely how character education is planned; then implementation, namely how character education is implemented; and evaluation, namely how character education is controlled. These functions must be realized in educational activities at school adequately which include the following aspects, including the values that need to be instilled, curriculum content, learning, assessment, educators and education staff or other related components.

Character education is carried out through development and learning experiences which lead to the formation of character values in students. This process is carried out through various processes of empowerment and acculturation as outlined as one of the principles of implementing national education.

C. RESEARCH PROCEDURES

Data sources in this research can be divided into two, namely humans/people and non-humans. Human data sources function as subjects or key informants. Meanwhile, non-human data sources are documents that are relevant to the research focus, such as images, photos, meeting notes or writings that are related to the research focus.

Determination of informants in this research is based on the following criteria: (1) the subject has long and intensive experience with the activity that is the target of the research, (2) the subject is still involved in the activity that is the target of the research, (3) the subject has sufficient time to be asked for information, (4) the subject is willing to provide actual information.

There are two types of data in this research, namely primary data and secondary data. The primary data in this research are the school principal, teachers and the community around the school. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained through studying various documents related to school principal policies.

The research instrument is a tool for collecting qualitative data that researchers get from the field. The main key in this research is the author himself because the researcher went into the field to observe and read the situation of the symptoms that emerged in the field. Apart from being a researcher, the role of observer is also carried out by the researcher,

because the researcher will interpret the findings in the field. In qualitative research, the methods used are interviews, observation and documentation.

D. RESEARCH DISCUSSION

1. Planning to Strengthen Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

Planning is the first step in the process of setting goals and selecting objectives, strategies, policies, procedures and programs that will be implemented by an educational institution. The meaning of planning itself is carried out by an organization or educational institution, in this case as a way of providing clarity regarding the objectives of each activity, so that its implementation gets results that are as effective and efficient as possible, adjusted to the existing resources in the organization. Likewise, the plans prepared by each school regarding the implementation of strengthening character education in improving the quality of learning are based on principles, mechanisms, standards, strategies and resource support in strengthening character education in improving student achievement.

Implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement, the concept departs from management as a process or series of activities integrating existing resources, which must also be integrated with the phasing in of the implementation of management functions, so that work can be realized as a quality producing activity. Every work in integrated quality management must be carried out through the stages of planning, preparation (including materials and tools), technical implementation with effective and efficient work methods/work methods, to produce products in the form of goods or services that are beneficial to society.

The development of planning for character education strengthening programs in improving student achievement is carried out in intracurricular and extracurricular activities starting from determining the vision, mission, goals and work plans, both medium term plans (RKJM) and annual work plans in the form of School Work Plans (RKS) and Budget Work Plans School (RKAS) in every work meeting.

2. Organizing Strengthening Character Education to Improve Student Achievement

This organizing process involves all parties in the school because the implementation of strengthening character education is carried out by all parties in the school. The preparation for strengthening character education physically, intellectually, aesthetically, ethically and spiritually is carried out comprehensively using intracurricular and extracurricular learning processes based on school culture.

The process of organizing the strengthening of character education in improving student achievement in the two schools has not proceeded according to the program plan. This is because each school does not maximize its work program, including character education that is tailored to its vision, mission and goals, as well as by referring to an analysis of its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges. This fact must be realized by stakeholders to become committed to building schools with character, one of

which is optimizing the role of extracurricular activities as a supplement to character education in schools. Optimizing extracurricular activities with an educational management approach in implementing character education is very necessary for the effectiveness and efficiency of achieving the goals of a school with character.

The organization of strengthening character education in improving student achievement at the school has not gone according to the program plan because the teacher's ability to prepare, develop and integrate character education into each work program for intracurricular and extracurricular activities has not been optimal. This is the influence in preparing the formula for strengthening character education in the learning process which is not optimal in strengthening character education activities.

3. Implementation of Strengthening Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

The implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement refers to Presidential Regulation Number 87 of 2017 concerning strengthening character education and Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education (PPK) in formal education units. Strengthening Character Education is an educational movement under the responsibility of the education unit to strengthen the character of students through harmonization of heart, feeling, thought, and exercise by involving and collaborating between educational units, families and society as a mental revolution movement. Management for strengthening character education prioritizes five main character values, namely religious, nationalist, independence, mutual cooperation and integrity. Strengthening these five character values will encourage students to have the 21st Century skills needed in life, such as critical thinking and problem solving skills, collaboration skills, creative skills and communication skills.

The implementation of character education, apart from the process of integrating learning with all subjects, is through developing students' personalities in extracurricular activity programs which have various extracurricular activities as a forum for forming, developing and nurturing students' talents and interests.

In applying integrated character education to intracurricular and extracurricular activities, it is developed through habits of life at school in participating in intracurricular and extracurricular activity programs as well as daily activities in school culture.

4. Supervision of Strengthening Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

Supervision is an activity to measure changes in student behavior that have been formed in intracurricular and extracurricular activities. The implementation of intracurricular and extracurricular activities in strengthening character education carried out by this school can present student behavior in the school culture in general. This activity is carried out in the context of daily correction for students, both behavior that violates school regulations and student achievements given to their school.

As for the form of character, it can be seen from students in their participation regarding attendance both when they come and go home, obeying the rules in intracurricular and extracurricular activities, and following the process of intracurricular and extracurricular activities. Then, the form of responsibility can be seen from students in carrying out and following the process in intracurricular and extracurricular activities, carrying out tasks, maintaining the cleanliness of the environment in extracurricular and extracurricular activities, maintaining and guarding school facilities and infrastructure.

5. Evaluation of Strengthening Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

Evaluation of the character education strengthening activity program in improving student achievement is carried out by the school within one academic year. This aims to evaluate and measure the extent of school programs, including work programs for intracurricular and extracurricular activities in strengthening character education. In carrying out an evaluation for one school year or two semesters, the school, in this case the supervising teacher, looks at the extent to which the work program is successful or not as an illustration for improving and evaluating in the following year.

6. Obstacles and Solutions to Strengthening Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

a. Internal Obstacles Related to the Implementation of Strengthening Character Education

The internal obstacles that occur are the gap between efforts to implement values at school and habits that have been embedded in the family environment and a lack of control from parents.

b. External Barriers to Implementing Strengthening Character Education

The external obstacles that occur are that there are some areas where the students' social environment does not support the growth of students' character.

Based on these inhibiting factors, the need for concern from the school committee or parents is still relatively minimal with minimal attention to their children's character development behavior, both at home and at school, especially in extracurricular activities. Another thing that is a problem is students' concern for their friends, their environment and their supervising teachers in realizing character education.

Problems and weaknesses in implementing character education management to strengthen character education in general can be internal and external. Internal factors are problems faced that are related to existing resources in the school environment, such as the school does not yet have potential resources, both human resources and other resources according to the standards for organizing extracurricular activities. .

Meanwhile, external factors are several problems, both directly and indirectly outside school resources which are related to the implementation of extracurricular activities in developing students' character regarding strengthening character education. The social

environment influences students' character more because students socialize with all elements of society, both positive and negative.

Solutions for Strengthening Character Education in Improving Student Achievement

The policy for implementing character education management in improving student achievement, both programmed in the RKS and in the curriculum as a whole, is in accordance with the school's vision and mission. Even though the programs implemented by schools regarding character education are not directly written in the school program planning, character cultivation has emerged directly from daily, weekly and monthly programs.

The habituation carried out by these programs has indirectly educated students' character, including strengthening character education. Even students independently carry out these activities so that students learn with discipline to display works through extra-curricular programs and are responsible for managing the implementation of events or events created in accordance with the goals to be achieved. In the future, the implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement in the school environment, including intracurricular and extracurricular activities in forming, developing and nurturing the character of students, can be carried out in order to produce students who have quality, and quality graduates who have character and achieve goals. Education primarily improves student achievement.

E. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Conclusion

- a. Schools as institutions that provide character education strengthening already have good plans to improve student achievement. The plans made by the school are outlined in the RKS, which are prepared at the beginning of the school year involving all relevant stakeholders.
- b. The organization of strengthening character education in improving student achievement has not gone according to the program plan. This is because each school does not maximize work programs, including character education that is tailored to the vision, mission and goals, as well as optimizing the role of extracurricular activities as a supplement to character education in schools.
- c. The implementation of strengthening character education is carried out by all stakeholders in the school environment, especially teaching staff who interact directly with students involved in the implementation of supervision.
- d. Control of strengthening character education is carried out in two stages, namely short-term evaluation carried out by teachers at the end of the teaching and learning process, this evaluation is called formative evaluation, and long-term evaluation.

- e. Barriers to strengthening character education in improving student achievement consist of internal and external barriers. The internal obstacles that occur are the gap between efforts to implement values at school and habits that have been embedded in the family environment and a lack of control from parents. Meanwhile, the external obstacles that occur are that there are some areas where the students' social environment is less supportive.
- f. Solutions to face obstacles to strengthening character education in realizing the Pancasila student profile are consolidation, equalizing perceptions, improving quality standards, short-term solutions, medium-term solutions and long-term solutions.

2. Recommendations

a. Government

The Education Department should be more committed to supporting the implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement so that they can achieve the desired goals according to government programs. The education department's commitment is concrete in monitoring, monitoring and evaluating up to providing assistance in the form of facilities and infrastructure or in the form of funds as well as education and training for teachers. .

b. Principal

School principals should be able to make various efforts to support and support the implementation of strengthening character education in improving student achievement. These efforts can take the form of actively overseeing activities to strengthen character education so that other teachers will be more active in efforts to strengthen character education. Apart from that, it can also strive to fulfill facilities and infrastructure as well as holding activities related to strengthening character education in improving student achievement.

c. For Teachers

For teachers to be able to oversee the implementation of strengthening character education in increasing student achievement even more optimally. Teachers must continue to innovate and be creative in ensuring that a culture of strengthening character education is created in schools by utilizing existing facilities and infrastructure in schools.

d. For Students

Students must be motivated to strengthen character education through social studies learning in various programs organized by schools, in order to become successful Indonesian people and have character in the future.

e. Public

The community in particular, namely parents, is expected to jointly play an active role in advancing the character education strengthening program in improving student achievement.

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